

EFFECT OF FIBER DISTRIBUTION ON COMBINED COMPRESSION-TORSIONAL RESPONSE OF HYBRID COMPOSITESSneha B. Cheryala¹ and Chandra S. Yerramalli²¹ Department of Aerospace Engineering, PhD student, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, India, sneha.c@aero.iitb.ac.in² Department of Aerospace Engineering, Associate Professor, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, India, chandra@aero.iitb.ac.in**Keywords:** Hybrid composite, fiber distribution, combined compression-torsion, Finite element analysis**ABSTRACT**

The objective of the current work is to study the role of fiber distribution in the combined loading response of hybrid glass/carbon composites using finite element analysis. The change in response with varying fiber distribution is presented taking into account of the different fiber location in the representative volume element (RVE). The results from the combined loading analysis show a noticeable interaction between the compression and shear response of the hybrid composite model, for both the cases of fiber distribution. The peak compressive strength was deteriorated by the addition of shear along with it. The model with symmetric glass/carbon fiber distribution had greater compressive strength and failure strain compared to the one with un-symmetric fiber distribution. An excessive shear deformation was noticed in the model with un-symmetric fiber distribution. The significance of fiber distribution in the combined loading response was dictated by the variation in the compressive strength with increasing shear, on the failure envelop.

1 INTRODUCTION

Material and geometric nonlinearity play a key role in the failure of composites under compressive loading. The stability of the structure under compression loading is determined by the various complicated failure mechanisms such as fiber micro-buckling, kinking and longitudinal splitting. The failure under compression initiates from the manufacturing defects such as fiber waviness or misalignment etc. Also, the compressive failure is majorly governed by shear properties of fiber and matrix.

Along with the above mentioned failure modes, the literature has accounted for some interesting aspects, influencing the failure under compression. The presence of different reinforcing materials in the same matrix material can considerably alter the mechanical properties and failure behavior of the entire composite. The effect of fiber mixing on the compression failure mode of carbon, Kevlar and glass fiber composites was investigated experimentally by Piggott and Harris[1]. Their experiments revealed that incorporation of glass into the carbon composites changed the initial kinking failure mode to splitting-kinking mode. In the case of carbon/Kevlar composites, the little addition of carbon to Kevlar composite reduced its ductility to a greater extent and enhanced its compressive strength. Addition of Kevlar to carbon modified the failure mode by the initiation of 45° shear cracking. Addition of glass to Kevlar composite changed the failure mode to fracture from initial localized kinking. Yerramalli and Waas [2] investigated the effect of strain rate on the compression failure strength from their static and dynamic compression tests on the glass/carbon hybrid composites. They noticed an increase in failure strength at high strain rates for all hybrid ratios. A 3D finite element analysis was carried out by Yerramalli and Waas [3] to study the fiber size effects in the glass and carbon composites. The results from the analysis clearly indicated an increase in compressive kinking strength with increasing fiber diameter. This was attributed to the larger fiber bending stiffness and higher fiber breaking strain of the fiber with larger diameter. A computational model to study the effect of fiber volume fractions and hybridization on the composite strengths was developed by Banerjee and Sankar [4]. They observed a drop in transverse compressive/tensile strength when glass is hybridized with carbon/epoxy. This was

because of the stress concentration caused by the high traverse modulus of the glass compared to the carbon fiber. They concluded that the fiber location did not make any difference to the stiffness properties as it is a volume averaged quantity. Their longitudinal tensile/compressive strength data was independent of fiber location unlike the transverse case. Their compressive strength data is indecisive as they did not incorporate the major failure governing phenomena like fiber micro-buckling and matrix yielding. The effect of relative fiber location along with fiber geometric imperfection on the compressive strength of hybrid glass/carbon composites was estimated by Koppisetty et al. [5]. Their results showed an increment in the compressive strength for symmetric fiber distribution in the composite. Also, the drop in compressive strength with increasing fiber geometric imperfection was due to excessive matrix yielding.

The effect of superimposed shear on the compressive strength of carbon/epoxy composite was investigated by Jelf and Fleck [6]. They detected that the failure was due to plastic micro-buckling of fibers similar to that of pure compression loading case. They noticed a linear drop in the compressive strength with increasing shear. From their experiments on combined compression shear response of carbon composites, Vogler et al. [7] and [8] did not observe any significant difference in the results from different loading paths. They declared the failure was due to the rotation of bent fibers inside the kink band without breaking in contrast to pure compression. Yerramalli and Waas [9] developed a fracture mechanics based failure criterion for combined loading response of unidirectional composites. Their experimental combined loading response display a substantial reduction in the compressive strength of pure glass and carbon composites when the shear stress attains a critical value. The glass composites failed by matrix crushing and splitting in the presence of remote shear stress along with compression.

From the literature, it was evident that, shear when accompanied with the compressive loading had a prominent influence on the failure behavior of the structure, when it reaches its critical value. And also, particularly in the case of hybrid composites, the placement of fibers inside the composite had a significant impact on the compressive strength. It is quite interesting to anticipate the situation where above two phenomena are coupled in a composite. Hence in the current work, an attempt is made to understand the effect of shear on the compressive response of hybrid composites for various fiber distributions using 3D finite element analysis. The 3D micromechanical models were assumed to be perfectly straight and geometric imperfections such as fiber misalignment were not considered, to exclusively understand the role played by the fiber distribution in the combined loading response.

2 MODELLING

The carbon/glass hybrid composite cylinders were modelled as 3D deformable solids using Abaqus software. The two models which differ only in their fiber distributions are shown in figure 1 [5]. Both the models have 36 carbon fibers and one glass fiber in each of them. While keeping the total fiber volume fraction (V_f) at 0.5, the total number of fibers in both the models is kept to 37 to display both the fiber distributions with ease for the given fiber geometry and V_f . The C36G1 model has its fibers distributed symmetrically with a central glass fiber surrounded by 36 carbon fibers. Whereas, C36G1S model has a shifted glass fiber to demonstrate the unsymmetrical fiber distribution. The comparison of modular centroids of the models are given in table 1.

Model	Modular Centroid (y,z) μm
C36G1	(0, 0)
C36G1S	(0, -2.215634)

Table 1: Comparison of modular centroids between C36G1 and C36G1S models

The diameter of glass fiber is $24.1\mu\text{m}$ and that of carbon is $5\mu\text{m}$. The content of glass (V_{fg}) in the total V_f is 0.195 and the carbon content is (V_{fc}) 0.305. The total length (L) of each composite is $82\mu\text{m}$ and the cross sectional radius (R) is $28\mu\text{m}$. The fibers were modelled as perfect-linearly elastic and the matrix behavior is nonlinear elastic-plastic. The transverse isotropic properties of carbon fiber are: $E_{11}=270\text{GPa}$, $E_{22}=E_{33}=8.76\text{GPa}$, $G_{12}=G_{13}=12\text{GPa}$, $G_{23}=3.244\text{GPa}$ and the Poisson ratio are: $\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}=\nu_{23}=0.35$. The isotropic glass fiber properties are: $E=72\text{GPa}$ and $\nu=0.22$ and, the vinyl ester resin has: $E_m=3.585\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_m=0.36$.

1) C36G1 model
(Symmetric fiber
distribution)

2) C36G1S model
(Un-symmetric fiber
distribution)

Figure 1: The cross sectional view of the selected hybrid models. Where, C36G1 model has symmetric fiber distribution and C36G1S model has a shifted glass fiber making it un-symmetric [5].

2.1 LOADING AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

In the finite element analysis, the models were meshed with C3D8R elements and hourglass stiffness was enhanced to avoid excessive deformation of the elements. Beam type multipoint constraint (MPC-node) was created separately for the loading face and the bottom face to apply the appropriate boundary conditions for all the loading cases as shown in Figure 2. The hybrid composite models were loaded proportionally in displacement (Δ) and rotation control ($R\theta$) at loading face MPC and, the reaction forces and moments were obtained from the same. The boundary conditions corresponding to pure compression, pure torsion and combined compression torsion are given in Tables 2, 3 and 4 respectively.

	U1	U2	U3	$\theta 1$	$\theta 2$	$\theta 3$
Loading Face MPC	Δ	Free	Free	Free	Fixed	Fixed
Bottom face MPC	Fixed	Free	Free	Free	Free	Free

Table 2: Compression loading.

	U1	U2	U3	$\theta 1$	$\theta 2$	$\theta 3$
Loading Face MPC	Fixed	Fixed	Fixed	0	Fixed	Fixed
Bottom face MPC	Free	Free	Free	Fixed	Free	Free

Table 3: Torsional loading.

	U1	U2	U3	$\theta 1$	$\theta 2$	$\theta 3$
Loading Face MPC	Δ	Free	Free	0	Fixed	Fixed
Bottom face MPC	Fixed	Free	Free	Fixed	Free	Free

Table 4: Combined Compression torsion loading.

Under combined loading the hybrid models were subjected to proportional axial displacement and rotation. The models were analyzed for various combined loading ratios ($\Delta/R\theta$) to derive the trend followed by the response with varying shear. The typical loading paths considered here are shown in figure 3. Where, the axial compressive strain was shown to be linear with shear strain indicating a proportional variation for all the loading ratios considered.

Figure 2: Boundary conditions applied to the multipoint constraint (MPC) of the loading and bottom face.

Figure 3: Proportional variation of axial compressive strain with shear strain for each loading path at various values of loading ratio ($\Delta/R\theta$).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the combined loading finite element analysis are shown in figure 4 for a loading ratio of 0.2. In the initial stages of loading the response curve is linear. With the further increase in load, the axial compressive stress nonlinearly increased with the increase in shear stress. The nonlinearity in the compressive response is induced due to its interaction with the applied shear. A peak value of shear is reached when the shear strain induced due to the combined compression exceeds the applied shear, causing relaxation in the torque at the MPC. This can be clearly explained from the drop in shear stress with increasing shear strain in figure 5. If the combined loading experiments are carried out under load control (torque control), at peak value of shear, the failure occurs catastrophically in torsion. This can be avoided by conducting the experiments in displacement/rotation control.

The increase in compression induced shear causes local yielding of the matrix and leads to initiation of kink bands. The shear response curve from the combined loading case is highly nonlinear compared

to that of pure torsional response. It was noticed that the model with un-symmetric fiber distribution has undergone excessive shearing. The further increase in combined loading causes rotation of fibers inside the kink band while there is an increase in compressive stress (see figure 4). A peak value of compressive stress is reached when the micro-buckled kink band makes one complete circumferential rotation forming a helix in the waisted section. This leads to splitting of fiber matrix interface with in the kink band and causes an instability in compression. This indicates the failure of model in compression. But, from the numerical analysis it was observed that, with the further increase in displacement and rotation, the model can be excessively sheared at approximately constant axial stress till the ultimate collapse of the structure.

In figure 6, the axial compressive response for combined compression-torsion loading for a loading ratio (0.2) was compared to that of pure compression for both the hybrid models. The pure compressive response plotted for symmetric fiber distribution corresponds to a fiber misalignment of 0.25 degree. It can be observed that the model with symmetric fiber distribution has much higher peak compressive strength compared to the one with unsymmetrical fiber distribution. In the case of combined loading, the addition of proportional shear damaged the peak compressive strength further in case of un-symmetric fiber distribution. The post failure behavior in the case of pure compression loading had a snap-back in compressive stress for both the cases of fiber distribution. But it is high in the case of model with symmetric fiber distribution with 0.25 degree fiber imperfection. This effect disappeared for the case of combined loading due to the dominance of increased fiber misalignment on the composite failure with the applied shear. The post failure behavior in compression was dictated by the amount of matrix yielding.

Model		Compressive strain value			
		composite	resin	Carbon fiber	Glass fiber
Symmetric fiber distribution (C36G1)	Peak in shear	-0.00905762	-0.0091277	-0.00908211	-0.00884462
	Peak in compression	-0.0146206	-0.0144029	-0.0141219	-0.0160047
Unsymmetrical fiber distribution (C36G1S)	Peak in shear	-0.0073309	-0.00843747	-0.00794939	-0.00995967
	Peak in compression	-0.00959162	-0.00912915	-0.00865887	-0.0115618

Table 5: Comparison of axial strains in the composite and its constituents at load steps corresponding to peak in shear and peak in compression obtained from 3D finite element analysis, for both the models with different fiber distribution.

The experimental value of fiber failure strain from the literature [10] for glass and carbon fibers is 4.4%-5.5% and 1.5%-1.9% respectively. In table 5 the axial strains of the composite and its constituents are given for the combined loading response shown in figure 4. The strain values correspond to the peak in shear and peak in compression. It was noticed that at both the peaks, the drop in strength was due to failure in the matrix. Since, both the fibers have not reached their failure strain. Also, the failure strain for symmetric model was higher than that of the model with un-symmetrically distributed fibers. For a range of loading ratios, from the numerical analysis of the hybrid models, the failure envelop corresponding to peak in shear is plotted in figure 7 for both the fiber distributions. Similarly, the failure envelop corresponding to peak in compression is shown in figure 8. From the failure envelop data, it was clear that, compressive strength dropped linearly with the increase in shear from pure compression strength and, inclined towards pure torsional strength. The model with symmetric fiber distribution has recorded larger compressive strengths. The un-symmetric model at very low loading ratios ($\Delta/R\theta$), i.e. at high shear, failed only in compression. This implies that there was no drop in shear strength due to applied combined compression. In contrast, the symmetric model at very high loading ratios ($\Delta/R\theta$), i.e. at low shear, failed only in shear. Since the induced shear stress due to compression was much larger than the applied shear, there would be a drop only in the shear stress. This indicates that for this model at high loading ratios there was no drop in compressive strength due to applied combined shear. The

linear trend followed by the failure envelop data for both the failure modes, i.e. the failure in compression and torsion, is plotted in figure 9. It shows that the un-symmetric model has recorded lower strengths than that of the symmetric model, at both the cases of failure. Also, the peak in shear can be considered as the lower bound of failure under combined compression torsion loading, for both the cases of fiber distribution.

Figure 4: The variation of axial compressive stress with shear stress obtained from 3D finite element analysis, under combined compression-torsion loading at loading ratio $((\Delta/R\theta)=0.2)$.

Figure 5: The comparison of shear response from combined compression-torsion loading simulations at $((\Delta/R\theta)=0.2)$ with pure torsional response.

Figure 6: The comparison of axial compressive response from combined compression-torsion loading simulations at $((\Delta/R\theta)=0.2)$ with pure compressive response. The pure compressive response of symmetric fiber distribution corresponds to the initial fiber misalignment of 0.25 degree.

Figure 7: The combined compression-torsion failure envelop corresponding to peak in shear of glass/ carbon hybrid composites obtained from 3D finite element analysis with different fiber distributions.

Figure 8: The combined compression-torsion failure envelop corresponding to peak in compression of glass/ carbon hybrid composites obtained from 3D finite element analysis with different fiber distributions.

Figure 9: The comparison of the trends of the combined loading failure envelop data corresponding to failure in shear and failure in compression of glass/ carbon hybrid composites obtained from 3D finite element analysis with different fiber distributions.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Based on the combined loading simulation of the hybrid composite model, it was noticed that under proportional combined loading the failure in compression and torsion do not occur simultaneously. The strong interaction between the compression and shear was explained by the nonlinearity in the combined loading response curve. The failure initiated in shear with the yielding of matrix under the influence of compression induced shear. The failure in compression occurred later due to splitting of interface in the micro-buckled kink band. After the failure in compression, the models could be excessively sheared till

the ultimate collapse. Fiber distribution played a significant role in the combined loading response of the hybrid composites. The model with symmetric fiber distribution had larger values of compressive stress and failure strain compared to that of the un-symmetric fiber distribution. From the post compressive failure behavior, it was justified that having an un-symmetrical fiber distribution and/or presence of external shear is identical to introducing a geometric imperfection in to the composite. The addition of external shear on to the model with un-symmetric fiber distribution decreased the compressive strength further. The combined loading failure envelop has showed the linear trend followed by the drop in compressive strength from pure compression, tending towards pure torsion, with increasing shear, for a range of loading ratios. The lower bound of failure was obtained to be the failure in shear, for both the cases of fiber distribution.

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